

RESEARCH DATA POLICY

of the DAM research mission

mareXtreme

„Paths to improved risk management in
the area of marine extreme events and
natural hazards“

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Research Data Policy of the DAM research mission „*Paths to improved risk management in the area of marine extreme events and natural hazards*“ (in short: „mareXtreme“) funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, BMBF) and the German northern states

The central research data management of the research mission mareXtreme¹, the data managers of the four associated consortia, all consortia and their partners agree to comply with the following binding Research Data Policy in accordance with the consortia coordinators and the office of the German Marine Research Alliance (Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung, DAM²):

Guidelines and legal frameworks

Research data are handled according to the current versions of the applicable laws including the Act governing the use of public sector data³, the Act to promote electronic government⁴ and the General Data Protection Regulation of the EU⁵ and as required by the funders, taking into account the action plan for research data of the BMBF⁶, the grant allocation notices with its annexes and the cooperation agreements within the consortia, as well as the Code of Conduct of the German Research Foundation for Safeguarding Good Research Practice⁷. In line with the Research Data Guideline of the German Marine Research Alliance⁸, newly generated data are made available sustainably on a long-term basis adhering to the open access, open science and to the FAIR data principles⁹ (Findable – Accessible – Interoperable – Reusable).

Responsibilities

Each consortium provides, updates and implements a data management plan (DMP) in agreement with the above regulations and in close collaboration with the central research mission's data management. Quality control of the data as well as a workflow for delivery of metadata and data from observation to archive and publishing are carried out within the respective consortia. The central data management collaborates tightly with the data managers of the consortia which, in turn, have direct contact to the individual scientists. All data managers provide support and advice regarding, e.g. harmonization and standardization, archival, integration, and documentation of data and metadata. They also provide advice to scientists in the research mission on how to make data FAIR. Each consortium partner is responsible for secure data storage and long-term archiving of the generated digital research data in trusted data repositories according to the FAIR principles.

Data exchange and use during the mission/project period

During the project period, metadata are collected and shared by the scientists, e.g. via the Ocean Science Information System (OSIS) at GEOMAR¹⁰, Dataverse at TU Braunschweig (in prep.), the BODI system at BSH (in prep.), or via links to repositories or contact persons that are specified in the DMPs stored at the internal file server of the mareXtreme website¹, thus enabling data sharing within and between all consortia. Research results must be reproducible through access to metadata and

data. Data sharing is carried out in accordance with the cooperation agreements of the consortia. Confidentiality must be clearly communicated.

Data publication

Publication of research data and (co-)authorship must be in compliance with § 3 and § 5 NKBF 2017, version Dec. 2022, the cooperation agreements of the consortia and the Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice⁷. Research data must be archived and published in suitable, sustainably operated, trustworthy long-term repositories, e.g. PANGAEA¹¹, WDC-CLIMATE¹², GESIS Data Services¹³ or LeoPard¹⁴ with standardized metadata. The deposited data must be published as soon as possible and no later than two years after the data acquisition and may be subject to an embargo for a maximum of two further years. After expiry of the moratorium period, the data must be made public immediately and actively following the FAIR data principles^{8,9}. Appropriate time limits for data embargos must be noted down in the DMPs. According to the annex to the grant allocation notice, results must be published at the latest 9 months after the project ends. Whenever possible, results shall be published in open access (§ 5.2.1 NKBF 2017, version Dec. 2022). Funding must be acknowledged by indicating the DAM research mission mareXtreme, the consortium name and the partner-specific BMBF grant number.

Wider dissemination of data

Metadata of the research data published in appropriate data repositories will be harvested by and thus findable in the German Marine Data Portal¹⁵.

References

- 1 *mareXtreme*, <https://www.marextreme.de/en>
- 2 *Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung*, <https://www.allianz-meeresforschung.de/en>
- 3 *Act governing the use of public sector data*, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_dng/index.html
- 4 *Act to promote electronic government*, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_egovg/
- 5 *General Data Protection Regulation of the EU*, <https://gdpr-info.eu/>
- 6 *BMBF Aktionsplan Forschungsdaten*, https://www.bildung-forschung.digital/digitalezukunft/de/wissenschaft_und_forschung/forschungsdaten/forschungsdaten_node.html, https://www.bildung-forschung.digital/digitalezukunft/shareddocs/Downloads/files/163_20_faktenblatt_aktionsplan_3_final.pdf
- 7 Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct. 28 pp. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472827>
- 8 Wiemer, G. et al. DAM-Forschungsdatenleitlinie. 5 pp. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8341227>
- 9 Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- 10 *GEOMAR Ocean Science Information System*, <https://osis.geomar.de/app/>
- 11 Felden, J. et al. PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science. *Sci. Data* 10, 347 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02269-x>
- 12 *World Data Centre for Climate*, <https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>
- 13 *GESIS Data Services*, <https://www.gesis.org/en/data-services/share-data>
- 14 *LeoPARD - TU Braunschweig Publications And Research Data*, <https://leopard.tu-braunschweig.de/>
- 15 *German Marine Data Portal*, <https://marine-data.de/>